

A SORTING LINE FOR SEPARATING
WOOD WASTE INTO
USABLE FRACTIONS FOR
NEW WOOD-BASED PANELS

Wood waste often consists of a mix of wood-based materials including solid wood, wood-based panels (such as fibre- and particleboard), fine fractions and impurities. Impurities include physical contaminants such as metal, plastic, glass and textiles. Some wood items may also carry preservatives and surface finishes.

Until now, wood waste has mainly been used for energy recovery and particleboard production. As prices for virgin wood rise and raw materials become scarcer, there is growing demand to use wood waste in higher value applications such as fibreboard. However, this requires clean separation of the wood fractions, which remains challenging at industrial scale.

EcoReFibre addressed this challenge by demonstrating a multi-stage sorting line that recovers three output streams: a solid wood fraction, a fibreboard fraction and a remaining mixed fraction.

PROCESS

Pre-shredded wood waste with mixed chip dimensions is first screened to create a consistent fraction based on thickness. Adjustable roller gaps and roller speeds separate the stream into chips, fines, and oversized material. This screening step is essential to remove material that is too fine or too coarse.

The screened fraction then enters a cleaning unit that removes impurities (incl. metals, stones, plastics, etc.) in order of improving material quality before optical sorting. Optical sorting uses camera-based detection and AI-classification to achieve high purity, separating the mixed waste wood stream by wood types.

The system analyses items on the conveyor in fractions of a second relying on Machine Learning. Classification relies on optical features, including shape and break edge which helps distinguish fibre structure from wood particles even when coatings are present. At the end of the conveyor, items are diverted into separate streams through precisely timed pulses of compressed air.

A first optical sorting step recovers a solid wood fraction. A second step produces a fibreboard enriched fraction and a remaining mixed stream. A third step can be applied to further concentrate fibreboard chips as the final output.

ACHIEVEMENTS

The EcoReFibre sorting demonstration confirmed that high purity fractions can be recovered from wood waste. Solid wood was separated in a single sorting stage, reaching 95% purity. Fibreboard was recovered through a two-stage sorting approach, achieving 97% purity. In total, more than 100 tonnes of material were processed, supporting the industrial relevance of the technology.

The sorted material was further used in downstream trials to demonstrate new recycling pathways. Both recycled fibreboard and solid wood were broken down into fibres, and the resulting recycled fibres were then used to manufacture different fibreboard products.

FUTURE CHALLENGES

With feedstock sorted to 97% purity, small residual impurities remain and must be removed so they don't become visible on the panel surface, where they impair the finish and may cause micro holes during sanding or coating. On the one hand, this can be improved through better and early upstream material classification. On the other hand, ongoing work optimises the Machine Learning focusing on the optical sensors to strengthen contaminant detection and removal.

CIRCULARITY

As a renewable, bio-based, carbon storing material wood is a key driver for Europe's circular bioeconomy. Reintegrating post-consumer fibreboards and other wood waste into production of new products helps closing material loops and extend the lifespan of wood. Through such horizontal recycling, the material value is maintained and the dependence on virgin wood is reduced.

An innovative waste sorting line and smart recycling technologies enable end-of-life wood-based panels to be broken down into fibres and particles which are then reintegrated into new panel production. Industrial trials have shown that MDF can incorporate up to 25% recycled wood while achieving performance similar to reference panels. From an economic perspective, increasing recycling can help broaden the raw material base and support stabilising volatile virgin wood prices. Of course, also investments in recycling equipment and process adaption are required for industrial-scale production.

By fostering a circular value chain, from waste sorting to panel manufacturing, the EcoReFibre project contributes to the objectives of the Green Deal, in particular the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR) and supports the goals of the Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP).

KEY PRINCIPLES OF CIRCULAR BIOECONOMY INCLUDE:

- Designing products that minimise waste
- Multi-actor dialogue
- Improving resource and energy efficiency
- Using by-products and secondary raw materials
- Promoting awareness and social engagement

ECOREFIBRE CLOSING THE MATERIAL LOOP THROUGH:

- New and adapted technologies & methods
- New collaborations
- New and adapted infrastructure
- Lifecycle analysis
- Supportive regulations and standards
- New business models

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